

Kinetics and mechanism of the oxidation of aliphatic primary alcohols by benzyltriethylammonium chlorochromate

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Abstract : The oxidation of nine aliphatic primary alcohols by benzyltriethylammonium chlorochromate (BTEACC) in dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO) leads to the formation of corresponding aldehydes. The reaction is first order with respect to both BTEACC and the alcohol. The reaction is catalysed by hydrogen ions. The hydrogen-ion dependence has the form : $k_{\text{obs}} = a + b [\text{H}^+]$. The oxidation of [1,1-²H₂]ethanol (MeCD₂OH) exhibits a substantial primary kinetic isotope effect. The reaction has been studied in nineteen different organic solvents. The solvent effect was analysed using Taft's and Swain's multiparametric equations. The rate of oxidation is susceptible to both polar and steric effects of the substituents. A suitable mechanism has been proposed.

Keywords : Kinetics and mechanism, oxidation, primary alcohols, substituted chromates.

Halochromates have been used as mild and selective oxidizing reagents in synthetic organic chemistry¹. Benzyltriethylammonium chlorochromate (BTEACC) is also one of such compounds used for the oxidation of benzylic alcohols². In continuation of our earlier³ work with Cr^{VI}, we report here the kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of nine aliphatic primary alcohols by BTEACC in dimethylsulphoxide (DMSO) as solvent. The mechanistic aspects are discussed. A suitable mechanism has also been proposed.

Results and discussion

The oxidation of alcohols results in the formation of corresponding aldehydes. The overall reaction may be represented as eq. (1)

BTEACC undergoes two-electron change. This is in accordance with the earlier observations with PFC, PCC and BTEACC also⁴.

It has already been shown that both PFC and PCC⁴ act as two electron oxidants and are reduced to chromium(IV) species by determining the oxidation state of chromium by magnetic susceptibility, ESR and IR studies. The reaction is first order with respect to BTEACC. Further the pseudo-first order rate constant, k_{obs} , is independent of the initial concentration of BTEACC. The reaction is first order with

respect to the alcohol also (Table 1). The oxidation of alcohols, in an atmosphere of nitrogen, failed to induce polymerisation of acrylonitrile. Further, the addition of acrylonitrile did not affect the rate. This indicates that a one-electron oxidation, giving rise to free radicals, is unlikely in the present reaction (Table 1). The rates of oxidation of ten secondary alcohols were determined at different temperatures and the activation parameters were calculated (Table 1).

Table 1. Rate constants for the oxidation of ethanol by BTEACC at 298 K

$10^3 [\text{BTEACC}]$ (mol dm ⁻³)	[Alcohol] (mol dm ⁻³)	[TsOH] (mol dm ⁻³)	$10^4 k_{\text{obs}}$ (s ⁻¹)
1.00	0.10	0.00	13.7
1.00	0.20	0.00	27.6
1.00	0.40	0.00	55.1
1.00	0.60	0.00	83.3
1.00	0.80	0.00	108
1.00	1.00	0.00	144
2.00	0.20	0.00	28.2
4.00	0.20	0.00	27.5
6.00	0.20	0.00	28.0
8.00	0.20	0.00	27.1
1.00	0.10	0.10	16.2
1.00	0.10	0.20	18.7
1.00	0.10	0.40	23.5
1.00	0.10	0.60	27.7
1.00	0.10	0.80	32.9
1.00	0.10	1.00	38.2
1.00	0.40	0.00	55.8 ^d

^dcontinued 0.001 mol dm⁻³ acrylonitrile.

Kinetic isotope effect : To ascertain the importance of cleavage of the α -C-H bond in the rate-determining step,

Table 2. Rate constants and activation parameters for oxidation of alcohols, RCH₂OH, by BTEACC

Alcohol (R)	10 ⁴ k ₂ (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹) at				ΔH [#] (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔS [#] (J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	ΔG [#] (kJ mol ⁻¹)
	288 K	298 K	308 K	318 K			
H	0.97	2.97	9.28	26.1	81.3 ± 0.7	-40 ± 2	93.1 ± 0.5
Me	65.7	144	315	666	56.3 ± 0.5	-92 ± 2	83.5 ± 0.4
Et	108	234	495	990	53.8 ± 0.2	-96 ± 1	82.3 ± 0.2
<i>n</i> -Pr	198	405	792	1510	49.3 ± 0.3	-107 ± 1	81.0 ± 0.2
<i>n</i> -Bu	216	441	873	1640	48.9 ± 0.1	-107 ± 1	80.7 ± 0.1
<i>i</i> -Pr	333	639	1190	2210	45.4 ± 0.4	-116 ± 1	79.8 ± 0.3
ClCH ₂	1.62	4.23	10.8	27.0	68.8 ± 0.6	-79 ± 2	92.2 ± 0.5
MeOCH ₂	11.7	28.8	65.7	144	61.1 ± 0.1	-89 ± 1	87.5 ± 0.1
<i>t</i> -Bu	3750	5620	8390	13500	29.7 ± 1.0	-150 ± 3	74.4 ± 0.8
MeCD ₂	11.1	25.3	57.2	128	59.5 ± 0.7	-95 ± 2	87.8 ± 0.6
k _H /k _D	5.92	5.69	5.51	5.20			

oxidation of [1,1-²H₂]ethanol was studied. The results showed the presence of a substantial primary kinetic isotope effect (Table 2).

The reaction is catalyzed by hydrogen ions (Table 1). The hydrogen-ion dependence has the following form eq. (2). The values of *a* and *b*, for ethanol, are 1.37 ± 0.03 × 10⁻³ s⁻¹ and 2.41 ± 0.04 × 10⁻³ mol⁻¹ dm³ s⁻¹ respectively (*r*² = 0.9994).

$$k_{\text{obs}} = a + b [\text{H}^+] \quad (2)$$

The oxidation of ethanol was studied in 19 different organic solvents. The choice of solvent was limited due to the solubility of BTEACC and its reaction with primary and secondary alcohols. There was no reaction with the solvents chosen. The kinetics were similar in all the solvents. The values of *k*₂ are recorded in Table 3.

Table 3. Effect of solvents on the oxidation of ethanol by BTEACC at 298 K

Solvents	10 ³ k ₂ (s ⁻¹)	Solvents	10 ⁵ k ₂ (s ⁻¹)
Chloroform	43.6	Acetic acid	7.94
1,2-Dichloroethane	46.7	Cyclohexane	1.74
Dichloromethane	51.3	Toluene	12.0
DMSO	144	Acetophenone	64.6
Acetone	39.8	THF	20.9
<i>N,N</i> -Dimethylformamide	81.3	<i>t</i> -Butyl alcohol	18.2
Butanone	29.5	1,4-Dioxane	22.4
Nitrobenzene	60.3	1,2-Dimethoxyethane	13.2
Benzene	14.8	Carbon disulfide	6.46
Ethyl acetate	15.8		

The activation enthalpies and entropies of the oxidation of the nine aliphatic alcohols are linearly related (*r* = 0.9917). The value of isokinetic temperature evaluated⁵ from this plot is 491 ± 30 K. The correlation was tested and found genuine by applying Exner's criterion⁶. An Exner's plot between log *k*₂ at 288 K and at 318 K was linear (*r* = 0.9983). The value of isokinetic temperature evaluated from the Exner's plot is 530 ± 30 K. The linear isokinetic correlation implies that all the alcohols are oxidized by the same mechanism and the changes in rate are governed by

the changes in both the enthalpy and entropy of the activation.

The observed hydrogen-ion dependence suggests that the reaction follows two mechanistic pathways, one is acid-independent and the other is acid-dependent. The acid-catalysis may well be attributed to a protonation of BTEACC to yield a protonated Cr^{VI} species which is a stronger oxidant and electrophile (3).

Formation of a protonated Cr^{VI} species has earlier been postulated in the reactions of structurally similar PCC and PFC⁷.

Table 4. Temperature dependence of the reaction constant

Temp./K	ρ*	δ	<i>r</i> ²	<i>sd</i>	ψ
288	-1.71 ± 0.01	-0.80 ± 0.01	0.9998	0.009	0.02
298	-1.61 ± 0.02	-0.72 ± 0.01	0.9999	0.004	0.01
308	-1.55 ± 0.03	-0.62 ± 0.02	0.9991	0.034	0.03
318	-1.45 ± 0.01	-0.56 ± 0.01	0.9998	0.011	0.02

The rate constants of the oxidation, *k*₂, in eighteen solvents (CS₂ was not considered, as the complete range of solvent parameters was not available) did not yield any significant correlation in terms of the linear solvation energy relationship (LESR) of Kamlet and Taft⁸ (4).

$$\log k_2 = A_0 + p\pi^* + b\beta + a\alpha \quad (4)$$

$$\log k_2 = -4.31 + 1.62 (\pm 0.20) \pi^* + 0.18 (\pm 0.16) \beta + 0.12 (\pm 0.16) \alpha \quad (5)$$

$$R^2 = 0.8600; \text{sd} = 0.18; n = 18; \psi = 0.41$$

$$\log k_2 = -4.28 + 1.66 (\pm 0.19) \pi^* + 0.14 (\pm 0.15) \beta \quad (6)$$

$$R^2 = 0.8541; \text{sd} = 0.18; n = 18; \psi = 0.41$$

$$\log k_2 = -4.30 + 1.70 (\pm 0.18) \pi^* \quad (7)$$

$$r^2 = 0.8461; \text{sd} = 0.18; n = 18; \psi = 0.40$$

$$\log k_2 = -2.75 + 0.44 (\pm 0.36) \beta \quad (8)$$

$$r^2 = 0.0829; \text{sd} = 0.44; n = 18; \psi = 0.98$$

Here n is the number of data points and ψ is the Exner's statistical parameter⁶.

The data on the solvent effect were analysed in terms of Swain's⁹ eq. (9) of cation- and anion-solvating concept of the solvents also.

$$\log k_2 = aA + bB + C \quad (9)$$

Here A represents the anion-solvating power of the solvent and B the cation-solvating power. C is the intercept term. $(A + B)$ is postulated to represent the solvent polarity. The rates in different solvents were analysed in terms of eq. (9), separately with A and B and with $(A + B)$.

$$\log k_2 = 0.65 (\pm 0.04) A + 1.71 (\pm 0.03) B - 3.91 \quad (10)$$

$$R^2 = 0.9959; sd = 0.03; n = 19; \psi = 0.07$$

$$\log k_2 = 0.41 (\pm 0.57) A - 2.73 \quad (11)$$

$$r^2 = 0.0297; sd = 0.46; n = 19; \psi \doteq 1.00$$

$$\log k_2 = 1.66 (\pm 0.12) B - 3.61 \quad (12)$$

$$r^2 = 0.9210; sd = 0.13; n = 19; \psi = 0.29 \quad (13)$$

$$\log k_2 = 1.36 \pm 0.14 (A + B) - 3.88$$

$$r^2 = 0.8520; sd = 0.18; n = 19; \psi = 0.39$$

Here n is the number of data points and Ψ is the Exner's statistical parameter.

The rates of oxidation of ethanol in different solvents showed an excellent correlation in Swain's equation (cf. eq. (10)) with the cation-solvating power playing the major role. In fact, the cation-solvation alone account for *ca.* 99% of the data. The correlation with the anion-solvating power was very poor. The solvent polarity, represented by $(A + B)$, also accounted for *ca.* 85% of the data. In view of the fact that solvent polarity is able to account for *ca.* 85% of the data, an attempt was made to correlate the rate with the relative permittivity of the solvent. However, a plot of $\log k_2$ against the inverse of the relative permittivity is not linear ($r^2 = 0.5393$; $sd = 0.31$; $\psi = 0.70$).

Correlation analysis of reactivity : The rates of oxidation of the alcohols failed to yield any significant correlation separately with Taft's¹⁰ σ^* and E_s values eqs. (14) and (15).

$$\log k_2 = -2.15 (\pm 0.38) \Sigma \sigma^* - 1.61 \quad (14)$$

$$r^2 = 0.8186; sd = 0.49; \psi = 0.45; n = 9$$

$$\log k_2 = -1.07 (\pm 0.32) \Sigma E_s - 2.17 \quad (15)$$

$$r^2 = 0.6186; sd = 0.62; \psi = 0.49; n = 9$$

The rates were, therefore, correlated in terms of Pavelich-Taft's¹¹ dual substituent-parameter (DSP) eq. (16).

$$\log k_2 = \rho^* \sigma^* + \delta E_s + \log k_0 \quad (16)$$

The values of substituent constants were obtained from the compilation by Wiberg¹⁰. The correlations are excellent;

the reaction constants being negative (Table 4). There is no significant collinearity ($r^2 = 0.2322$) between σ^* and E_s values of the nine substituents.

The negative polar reaction constant indicates an electron-deficient carbon centre in the transition state of the rate-determining step. The negative steric reaction constant shows a steric acceleration of the reaction. This may be explained on the basis of high ground state energy of the sterically crowded alcohols. Since the crowding is relieved in the product aldehyde as well as in the transition state leading to it, the transition state energies of the crowded and uncrowded alcohols do not differ much and steric acceleration, therefore, results.

Mechanism :

The presence of a substantial primary kinetic isotope effect confirms the cleavage of an α -C-H bond in the rate-determining step. The large negative value of the polar reaction constant together with substantial deuterium isotope effect indicate that the transition state approaches a carbocation in character. Hence, the transfer of hydride-ion from alcohol to the oxidant is suggested. The hydride-transfer mechanism is also supported by the major role of cation-solvating power of the solvents.

The hydride ion transfer may take place either by a cyclic process via an ester intermediate or by an acyclic one-step bimolecular process. This postulation is supported by an analysis of the temperature dependence of kinetic isotope effect. Kwart and Nickle have shown that a study of the dependence of the kinetic isotope effect on temperature can be gainfully employed to resolve this problem. The data for protio- and deuterio-ethanols, fitted to the familiar expression $k_H/k_D = A_H/A_D \exp(\Delta E_d/RT)$ ¹² show a direct correspondence with the properties of a symmetrical transition state in which the activation energy difference (ΔE_a) for k_H/k_D is equal to the zero-point energy difference for the respective C-H and C-D bonds (≈ 4.5 kJ/mol) and the frequency factors and the entropies of activation of the respective reactions are nearly equal. The similar phenomena have also observed earlier in the oxidation of diols by BPCC¹³ and that of alcohols by PFC¹. Bordwell⁶ has documented a very cogent evidence against the occurrence of concerted one-step biomolecular processes by hydrogen transfer and it is evident that in the present studies also the hydrogen transfer does not occur by an acyclic biomolecular process. It is well established that intrinsically concerted sigmatropic reactions, characterized by transfer of hydrogen in a cyclic transition state, are the only truly symmetrical processes involving a linear hydrogen transfer¹⁴. Littler has also shown that a cyclic hydride transfer, in the oxida-

Mishra *et al.* : Kinetics and mechanism of the oxidation of aliphatic primary alcohols by benzyltriethylammonium *etc.* tion of alcohols by Cr^{VI} , involves six electrons and, being a Hückel-type system, is an allowed process¹⁵. Thus the overall mechanism is proposed to involve the formation of a chromate ester in a fast pre-equilibrium step and then a disproportionation of the ester in a subsequent slow step via a cyclic concerted symmetrical transition state leading to the product (Scheme 1). The observed hydrogen-ion dependence can be explained by assuming a rapid reversible protonation of the chromate ester (A) with the protonated ester decomposing at a rate faster than (A) (Scheme 2).

Scheme 1

Scheme 2

It is of interest to compare here the modes of oxidation of alcohols by BPCC¹³, QFC and BTEACC. The oxidation by QFC exhibited Michaelis-Menten type of kinetics with respect to alcohols. Whereas the oxidation by both, BPCC and BTEACC presented similar kinetic pictures i.e. the reaction is first order with respect to alcohols. The rate laws, hydrogen-ion dependence and kinetic isotope effect are similar in both the cases. In the oxidation of alcohols by halochromates excellent correlations were obtained in terms of Swain's equation. Though the data are not conclusive, it seems that the mode of oxidation depends upon the nature of the halogen present in the Cr^{VI} species and not on the nature of the base.

Experimental

Materials : BTEACC was prepared by the reported method² and its purity was checked by an iodometric method. The procedures used for the purification of alco-

hols have been described earlier¹⁶. [1,1-²H₂]ethanol (MeCD_2OH) was prepared by Kalpan's method¹⁷. Its isotopic purity, as ascertained by its NMR spectra, was $95 \pm 2\%$. Due to the non-aqueous nature of the medium, *p*-toluenesulphonic acid (TsOH) was used as a source of hydrogen ions. TsOH is a strong acid and in a polar medium like DMSO it is likely to be completely ionised. Solvents were purified by the usual method¹⁸.

Product analysis : The product analysis was carried out under kinetic conditions. In a typical experiment, ethanol (2.30 g, 0.05 mol) and BTEACC (3.10 g, 0.01 mol) were made up to 50 cm^3 in DMSO and kept in dark for *ca.* 15 h to ensure completion of the reaction. The solution was then treated with an excess (200 cm^3) of a saturated solution of 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine in 2 mol dm^{-3} HCl and kept overnight in a refrigerator. The precipitated 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone (DNP) was filtered off, dried, weighed, recrystallized from ethanol and weighed again. The yield of DNP before and after recrystallization was 2.04 g (92%) and 1.77 g (78%), respectively. The DNP was found identical (m.p. and mixed m.p.) with the DNP of acetaldehyde. Similar experiments with other alcohols led to the formation of DNP of the corresponding carbonyl compounds in yields ranging from 72 to 84%, after recrystallization. Iodometric determinations of the oxidation state of chromium in completely reduced reaction mixtures indicated that the oxidation state of the reduced chromium species was 3.90 ± 0.15 .

Kinetic measurements : The reactions were followed under pseudo-first order conditions by keeping a large excess ($\times 15$ or greater) of the alcohol over BTEACC. The temperature was kept constant to $\pm 0.1 \text{ K}$. The solvent was DMSO, unless specified otherwise. The reactions were followed by monitoring the decrease in the concentration of BTEACC spectrophotometrically at 370 nm for 80% of the reaction. The pseudo-first order rate constants, k_{obs} , were evaluated from the linear ($r = 0.990-0.999$) plots of $\log [\text{BTEACC}]$ against time. Duplicate kinetic runs showed that the rate constants were reproducible to within $\pm 3\%$. The second order rate constant, k_2 , was evaluated from the relation $k_2 = k_{\text{obs}}/[\text{alcohol}]$. Simple and multivariate linear regression analyses were carried out by the least-squares method on a personal computer.

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